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**POLYVARIANCE OF RESPONSES TO BALNEOTHERAPY OF
CLEARANCE AND FRACTIONAL EXCRETION OF URIC ACID AND
CONCOMITANT CHANGES IN PARAMETERS OF THE NEURO-
ENDOCRINE-IMMUNE COMPLEX AND METABOLISM**

Ishchenko V.S.

*International Humanitarian University, Odessa, Ukraine
ishchenkovov@gmail.com*

**ПОЛІВАРІАНТНІСТЬ РЕАКЦІЇ НА БАЛЬНЕОТЕРАПІЮ КЛІРЕНСУ ТА
ФРАКЦІЙНОГО ВИВЕДЕННЯ СЕЧОВОЇ КИСЛОТИ ТА СУПУТНІ
ЗМІНИ ПАРАМЕТРІВ НЕЙРО-ЕНДОКРИННО-ІМУННОГО
КОМПЛЕКСУ ТА МЕТАБОЛІЗМУ**

Іщенко В.С.

*Міжнародний гуманітарний університет, Одеса, Україна
ishchenkovov@gmail.com*

Authors Information

Ishchenko V.S. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3777-8636>

Summary/Резюме

Background. In the process of implementing the project “Neuro-endocrine regulation of the clearance of nitrogenous metabolites”, we identified quantitative-qualitative clusters of clearance, their specific accompaniment by a constellation of EEG, HRV, hormones, blood pressure, metabolism and immunity indicators, as well as their correlations. At the same time, the term of examination was not taken into account, that is, the state before or after the course of balneotherapy. Therefore, the aim of this study was to identify variants of *reactions to balneotherapy* of clearance and fractional excretion of uric acid and concomitant changes in the parameters of the neuro-endocrine-immune complex and metabolism.

Materials and Methods. The object of observations were patients with chronic pyelonephritis in the phase of remission (34 males aged 23-70 years and 10 females aged 33-76 years). Testing was performed twice — on admission and after 7-10 days of standard balneotherapy on the Truskavets’ Spa. Creatinine and uric acid levels were determined in daily urine and serum to calculate clearance and fractional excretion. In addition, levels of a number of other metabolites, key adaptive hormones, and immune markers was determined. The state of the autonomic and central nervous systems was assessed by the HRV and EEG methods respectively. Immune status evaluated by routine methods.

Results. 5 clusters of uric acid clearance (C) and fractional excretion (FE) reactions were identified. Significant increase in C combined with a moderate decrease in FE in 20.5 % of patients; moderate increase in C in the absence of significant changes in FE in 34.5 %; no significant changes in C combined with a moderate decrease in FE in 18.2 %; moderate decrease in C combined with a significant decrease in FE in 13.6 %; significant decrease in C combined with a moderate decrease in FE in 13.6 % of patients. Each cluster is accompanied by characteristic changes in 9 EEG parameters, 2 HRV, 2 immunity, 9 metabolic, as well as cortisol and diastolic blood pressure levels, in the aggregate of which all 5 clusters clearly differ from each other and are recognized with 100 % accuracy.

Conclusion. Both clearance and fractional excretion of uric acid respond to balneotherapy factors, but to different degrees and even in different directions in one of the 5 clusters. This is accompanied by characteristic changes in a number of parameters of the neuro-endocrine-immune complex, metabolism and diastolic pressure, among which one should distinguish factorial, concomitant and consequential.

Keywords: *uric acid clearance and fractional excretion, EEG, HRV, adaptation hormones, immunity, metabolism, chronic pyelonephritis.*

Передумови. В процесі реалізації проєкту “Нейро-ендокринна регуляція кліренсу азотистих метаболітів” ми виявили кількісно-якісні кластери кліренсу, їх специфічний супровід констеляцією показників EEG, ВРС, гормонів, артеріального тиску, метаболізму та імунітету, а також їх кореляційні зв’язки. При цьому не брали до уваги термін обстеження, тобто стан до чи після курсу бальнеотерапії. Тому метою даного дослідження стало виявлення варіантів *реакцій на бальнеотерапію* кліренсу і фракційної екскреції сечової кислоти та супутніх змін параметрів нейро-ендокринно-імунного комплексу і метаболізму.

Матеріали та методи. Об’єктом спостереження були пацієнти з хронічним пієлонефритом у фазі ремісії (34 чоловіки віком 23-70 років та 10 жінок віком 33-76 років). Тестування проводилося двічі — при поступленні та після 7-10 днів стандартної бальнеотерапії на курорті Трускавець. Визначався вміст креатиніну та сечової кислоти у добовій сечі та сироватці крові для розрахунку її кліренсу і фракційної екскреції. Крім того, визначався рівень низки інших метаболітів, основних адаптаційних гормонів та імунних показників. Стан вегетативної та центральної нервової систем оцінювався методами ВРС та EEG відповідно. Імунний статус оцінювався рутинними методами.

Результати. Виявлено 5 кластерів реакцій кліренсу (С) і фракційної екскреції (FE) сечової кислоти. Значне збільшення С в поєднанні з помірним зменшенням FE у 20,5 % пацієнтів; помірне збільшення С за відсутності значущих змін FE у 34,5 %; відсутність значущих змін С в поєднанні з помірним зменшенням FE у 18,2 %; помірне зменшення С в поєднанні зі значним зменшенням FE у 13,6 %; значне зменшення С в поєднанні з помірним зменшенням FE у 13,6 %. Кожен кластер супроводжується характерними змінами 9 параметрів EEG, 2 ВРС, 2 імунітету, 9 метаболічних, а також рівнів кортизолу і діастолічного тиску, за сукупністю яких всі 5 кластерів чітко відрізняються один від одного та розпізнаються з точністю 100 %.

Висновок. Як кліренс, так і фракційна екскреція сечової кислоти реагують на фактори бальнеотерапії, але різною мірою і навіть різноскеровано в одному із 5 кластерів. Це супроводжується характерними змінами низки параметрів нейро-ендокринно-імунного комплексу, метаболізму і діастолічного тиску, серед яких слід розрізняти факторні, супутні і наслідкові.

Ключові слова: *кліренс та фракційна екскреція сечової кислоти, EEG, ВРС, гормони адаптації, імунітет, метаболізм, хронічний пієлонефрит.*

Introduction

On the first stage of project “Neuro-endocrine regulation of the clearance of nitrogenous metabolites” implementation, we found out of peculiarities of metabolic and neuro-endocrine accompaniments of urate-losing and urate-retaining kidneys. Using the meth-

od of discriminant analysis, it was found that constitutionally distinct types of uric acid metabolism are characterized, in addition to clearance, uricosuria and uricemia by definition, by specific constellations of 11 metabolic and 7 autonomic variables as well as serum calcitonin and Stange’s test [Ishchenko

VS et al., 2024]. In second study, performed on the same sample of patients, the battery of tests was supplemented with electroencephalography and immunity. The method of discriminant analysis revealed 32 variables (in addition to clearance, fractional excretion, uricosuria and uricemia by definition, 14 EEG, 7 HRV, 4 blood pressure, and 3 endocrine), according to the totality of which all 4 clusters of uric acid clearance clearly differ from each other (classification accuracy 100 %) [Ishchenko VS & Anchev AS, 2024]. In third study, was analyzed the relationships between uric acid clearance and neurogenic, endocrine and immune variables and identified among them the factors regulating the former. It is shown that uric acid clearance is subject to the regulatory effects of central and autonomous nervous as well as endocrine and immune systems. The closest relationship revealed between PSD of LF band HRV as marker of vagal tone and baroreflex activity. In addition, other vagal markers have a upregulating effect, while markers of sympathetic tone have a downregulating effect. Taken together, autonomic influences determine uric acid clearance by 37.6 %. The influence of the central nervous system on uric acid clearance was significantly weaker than that of the autonomic system (20.1 %). Taken together, autonomic and central neurogenic influences determine uric acid clearance by 47.8 %. Other enhancing factors is diastolic blood pressure, whereas the Stange's test and the intensity of the phagocytic function of blood neutrophils are downregulating factors. This neuro-endocrine-immune constellation of regulatory factors determines uric acid clearance by 62.5 % [Gozhenko AI & Ishchenko VS, 2025].

At the same time, the term of examination was not taken into account, that is, the state before or after the course of balneotherapy. Therefore, the aim of this study was to identify variants of *reactions to balneotherapy* of clearance and fractional excretion of uric acid and concomitant changes in the parameters of the neuro-endocrine-immune complex and metabolism.

Scientific novelty. For the first time, five qualitatively distinct clusters of reactions of

clearance and fractional excretion of uric acid to balneotherapy were identified using the iterative k-means method and specific patterns of concomitant changes in the parameters of the neuro-endocrine-immune complex and metabolism were established for each cluster. The results justify the need to transition from an averaged group to an individualized cluster approach when prescribing and assessing the effectiveness of balneotherapy.

Material and methods

Participants. The objects of the study were patients with chronic pyelonephritis in remission, verified by clinical, laboratory and instrumental criteria. The study included 34 men aged 23–70 years and 10 women aged 33–76 years. Inclusion criteria: chronic pyelonephritis in remission, no exacerbation for at least 3 months before balneotherapy, preserved nitrogen-excreting kidney function (serum creatinine level within normal limits) and functional renal reserve [Hozhenko AI et al., 2015]. Exclusion criteria: acute urinary tract infection, history of gout or hyperuricemia, taking uricolytic or uricosuric drugs within 3 months before the study, decompensated concomitant diseases of the cardiovascular system, diabetes mellitus, oncological diseases. All patients signed an informed consent to participate in the study. The study was approved by the local ethics committee in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

Testing was performed twice — on admission and after 7-10 days of standard balneotherapy on Truskavets' Spa (drinking of Naftussya bioactive water, applications of ozokerite, mineral pools) [Chebanenko OI et al., 1997; Ruzhylo SV et al., 2003; Lukovych YuS et al., 2015].

Procedure / Test protocol / Skill test trial / Measure / Instruments. The battery of tests was created in line with concepts functional-metabolic continuum [Gozhenko AI, 2016] and neuro-endocrine-immune complex [Popovych IL et al., 2022; Korda MM et al., 2024]. The day before, daily urine was collected, in which was determined the concentration of uric acid (estimated by uricase meth-

od), creatinine (by Jaffe's color reaction by Popper's method) and urea (urease method by reaction with phenolhypochlorite) as well as electrolytes: calcium (by reaction with arsenase III), magnesium (by reaction with colgamite), phosphates (phosphate-molybdate method), chloride (mercury-rhodanidine method), sodium and potassium (flaming photometry). The analysis carried out according to instructions [Goryachkovskiy AM, 1998]

The same metabolic parameters were determined in serum as well as glucose (glucose-oxidase method), total cholesterol and content of it in composition of HD, LD and VLD lipoproteins [Goryachkovskiy AM, 1998]; diene conjugates (spectrophotometry of heptane phase of lipids extract) [Gavrilov VB & Mishkorudnaya MI, 1983] and malondialdehyde (test with tiobarbiture acid) [Andreyeva LI et al., 1988], as well as the activity of anti-oxidant enzymes: catalase serum (by the speed of decomposition hydrogen peroxide) [Korolyuk MA et al., 1988] and superoxide dismutase erythrocytes (by the degree of inhibition of nitroblue tetrazolium recovery in the presence of N-methylphenazone metasulfate and NADH) [Makarenko YeV, 1988; Dubinina YY et al., 1988].

The analysis carried out with the use of flaming spectrophotometer "СФ-46", analyzers "Reflotron" (BRD) and "Pointe-180" (USA) and corresponding sets of reagents.

In addition, we determined serum levels of main adaptation hormones such as Cortisol, Aldosterone, Testosterone, Triiodothyronine, Calcitonin and PTH as well as C-reactive protein (by the ELISA with the use of analyzer "RT-2100C" and corresponding sets of reagents from "Алкор Био", XEMA Co, Ltd and DRG International Inc). Systolic (Ps) and diastolic (Pd) blood pressure was measured (tonometer "Omron M4-I", Netherlands) in a sitting position three times in a row followed by the calculation of Ps2/Ps1, Ps3/Ps1, Pd2/Pd1, and Pd3/Pd2 rations [Popovych IL et al., 2022]. The good old Stange's and Genchi's tests were carried out on occasion [Biletsky SV & Gozhenko AI, 2007].

To assess the parameters of heart rate

variability (HRV), recorded electrocardiogram during 7 min in II lead (hardware-software complex "CardioLab+HRV" produced by "KhAI-Medica", Kharkiv, Ukraine). For further analyses the following parameters HRV were selected. Temporal parameters (Time Domain Methods): heart rate (HR), the standard deviation of all NN intervals (SDNN), the square root of the mean of the sum of the squares of differences between adjacent NN intervals (RMSSD), the percent of interval differences of successive NN intervals greater than 50 ms (pNN₅₀), triangular index (TNN). Spectral parameters (Frequency Domain Methods): power spectral density (PSD) bands of HRV: high-frequency (HF, range 0,4ч0,15 Hz), low-frequency (LF, range 0,15ч0,04 Hz), very low-frequency (VLF, range 0,04ч0,015 Hz) and ultralow-frequency (ULF, range 0,015ч0,003 Hz). We calculated classical indexes: LF/HF, LFnu = 100 % • LF / (LF+HF), Centralization Index (VLF+LF)/HF [Heart Rate Variability, 1996; Berntson GG et al., 1997; Baevsky R. & Chernikova A 2017; Shaffer F & Ginsberg JP, 2017].

Simultaneously EEG recorded a hardware-software complex "NeuroCom Standard" (KhAI Medica, Kharkiv, Ukraine) monopolar in 16 loci (Fp1, Fp2, F3, F4, F7, F8, C3, C4, T3, T4, P3, P4, T5, T6, O1, O2) by 10-20 international system, with the reference electrodes A and Ref on the earlobes. Two minutes after the eyes had been closed, 25 sec of artifact free EEG data were collected by computer. Among the options considered the average EEG amplitude (mV), average frequency (Hz), frequency deviation (Hz), index (%), coefficient of asymmetry (%), absolute (mV²/Hz) and relative (%) PSD of basic rhythms: β (35 - 13 Hz), α (13 - 8 Hz), и (8 - 4 Hz) and δ (4 - 0,5 Hz) in all loci, according to the instructions of the device. In addition, calculated coefficient of Asymmetry (As) and Laterality Index (LI) for PSD each Rhythm using formulas:

$$As, \% = 100 \cdot (Max - Min) / Min; LI, \% = \Sigma[200 \cdot (Right - Left) / (Right + Left)] / 8.$$

We calculated for each locus EEG the Entropy (h) of normalized PSD using Popovych's IL formulas [Popadynets' OO et al.,

2020; Gozhenko AI et al., 2021; Popovych IL et al, 2022] based on classic Shannon's CE [1948] formula:

$$h_{EEG} = -[PSD_{\alpha} \cdot \log_2 PSD_{\alpha} + PSD_{\beta} \cdot \log_2 PSD_{\beta} + PSD_{\theta} \cdot \log_2 PSD_{\theta} + PSD_{\delta} \cdot \log_2 PSD_{\delta}] / \log_2 4.$$

Immune status evaluated as described in the manuals [Lapovets' LYe &, Lutsyk BD, 2004]. For phenotyping subpopulations of lymphocytes used the methods of rosette formation with sheep erythrocytes on which adsorbed monoclonal antibodies against receptors CD3, CD4, CD8, CD22 and CD56 from company "Granum" (Kharkiv) with visualization under light microscope with immersion system. The state of humoral immunity judged by the concentration in serum of Immunoglobulins of classes G, A, M (ELISA analyser "Immunochem", USA) and circulating immune complexes (by polyethylene glycol precipitation method).

Parameters of phagocytic function of neutrophils estimated as described by Kovbasnyuk MM [Kulchynskiy AB et al., 2016]. The objects of phagocytosis served daily cultures of *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC N 25423 F49) as typical specimen for Gram-positive Bacteria and *Escherichia coli* (O55 K59) as typical representative of Gram-negative Bacteria. Take into account the following parameters of Phagocytosis: activity (percentage of neutrophils, in which found microbes — Hamburger's Phagocytic Index PhI), intensity (number of microbes absorbed one phagocytes — Microbial Count MC or Right's Index) and completeness (percentage of dead microbes — Killing Index KI).

At last, we evaluated the tone and motility of gall-bladder by its volume on an empty stomach and after 5, 15 and 30 min after ingestion of cholekinetic (50 ml of 40 % solution of xylitol). The method echoscopy (echocamera "Radmir") applied. To quantify cholekinetics, the area between the cholecystovolumogram and the basal line was calculated [Marfiyan OM et al., 2015].

Normal (reference) values of variables are taken from the instructions and/or database of our group [Hozhenlo AI et al., 2015;

Gozhenlo AI et al., 2021; Popovych IL et al., 2022; Babelyuk VY et al., 2023].

For statistical analysis used the software package "Microsoft Excel" and "Statistica 6.4 StatSoft Inc" (Tulsa, OK, USA).

Study limitations. The authors acknowledge that the sample size (44 patients) is relatively small, especially for clusters of 6 patients, which limits the statistical power of pairwise comparisons in subgroups. The marked gender imbalance (34 men vs. 10 women) may have influenced the results given the known sex differences in uric acid metabolism. The lack of a control group without balneotherapy makes it impossible to completely exclude spontaneous dynamics of indicators. The single-center design limits the external validity of the results. These limitations determine the need to confirm the obtained results in multicenter studies with larger samples.

Fig. 1. Scatterplot of correlation between Clearance of Uric acid (X-line) and its Fractional Excretion (Y-line)

Fig. 2. Scatterplot of correlation between changes in Clearance of Uric acid (X-line) and its Fractional Excretion (Y-line)

Table 1
Members of Clusters of changes in C&FE of Uric acid and Distances from Respective Cluster Center

Members of Cluster Number 1 and Distances from Respective Cluster Center Cluster contains 6 cases	
Case No.	Distance
C_14	1,65
C_20	4,76
C_30	0,70
C_35	1,56
C_37	0,74
C_44	1,51

Members of Cluster Number 2 and Distances from Respective Cluster Center Cluster contains 6 cases	
Case No.	Distance
C_11	1,07
C_22	0,72
C_28	1,00
C_36	1,07
C_39	0,35
C_40	0,84

Members of Cluster Number 3 and Distances from Respective Cluster Center Cluster contains 15 cases	
Case No.	Distance
C_2	0,30
C_3	0,71
C_4	0,63
C_5	0,90
C_9	0,60
C_10	0,44
C_15	1,04
C_16	0,10
C_19	0,09
C_25	0,59
C_26	0,14
C_31	0,58
C_33	0,16
C_34	0,34
C_38	0,07

Members of Cluster Number 4 and Distances from Respective Cluster Center Cluster contains 9 cases	
Case No.	Distance
C_6	0,67
C_12	0,22
C_13	1,05
C_17	2,26
C_23	0,79
C_24	1,27
C_27	1,08
C_41	0,68
C_42	0,03

Members of Cluster Number 5 and Distances from Respective Cluster Center Cluster contains 8 cases	
Case No.	Distance
C_1	1,07
C_7	0,36
C_8	1,05
C_18	0,98
C_21	0,31
C_29	0,74
C_32	0,59
C_43	0,52

Results

At the preparatory stage, it was found that the correlation between Clearance of Uric acid and its Fractional Excretion is moderate

(Fig. 1), and the correlation between their changes after balneotherapy is generally weak (Fig. 2). This fact confirms the relative independence of glomerular filtration and tubular transport of urate and justifies the need for simultaneous analysis of both indicators.

Immediately, attention is drawn to the drastic decrease in FEUA in patient Dr (by 74.7 %), i.e. there is a so-called “falling value”, which usually needs to be removed from the subsequent analysis as an artifact [Anscombe FJ, 1973; Chatterjee S & Firat A, 2007]. However, our group has demonstrated that this results in the loss of unique valuable information [Gozhenko A, Zantaraia T, Zukow W, 2024]. Therefore, we also ignored the recommendation and left the data of patient Dr for subsequent analysis. Arguments in favor of such a decision will be given later.

At the next stage, the reactions were fragmented into separate clusters. Clustering by changes in C and FE was implemented by iterative k-means method [Aldenderfer MS & Blashfield RK, 1989]. In this method, the object is assigned to the class to which the Euclidean distance is minimal. The main principle of the structural approach to the selection of homogeneous groups is that objects of the same class are close, and objects of different classes are distant. In other words, a cluster (image) is a collection of points in an n-dimensional geometric space in which the average inter-point distance is less than the average distance from these points to the rest. The results of the cluster analysis are shown in Table 1.

5 clusters of uric acid clearance (C) and fractional excretion (FE) reactions were identified. Significant increase in C combined with a moderate decrease in FE in 20.5 % of patients; moderate increase in C in the absence of significant changes in FE in 34.5 %; no significant changes in C combined with a moderate decrease in FE in 18.2 %; moderate decrease in C combined with a significant decrease in FE in 13.6 %; significant decrease in C combined with a moderate decrease in FE in 13.6 % of patients.

Repeated correlation analysis revealed (Fig. 3) that in the C2-FE- cluster the relation-

Fig. 3. Scatterplot of correlation between changes in Clearance of Uric acid (X-line) and its Fractional Excretion (Y-line) in various Clusters

ship between changes in both parameters is strong and direct, while in the C0FE- cluster it is moderate and inverse, with no significant correlation in the C2+FE- and C+FE0 clusters.

The moderate and direct relationship in the C-FE2- cluster is due only to the aforementioned drastic decrease in FE from 87.5 % to 12.8 % due to a decrease in urinary UA concentration from an abnormally high 11.3 mM/L to 2.8 mM/L in the absence of significant changes in normal serum concentrations of both UA and creatinine. At the same time, the initial uricosuria was increased very moderately (5.20 mM/24h) due to a significantly reduced diuresis (0.46 L/24h), so that C decreased from 11.64 mL/min to 7.53 mL/min.

This unique case will be described in more detail in a separate article, and in this article we will limit ourselves to stating the facts that in patient Dr, an abnormally high level of FEUA was accompanied by abnormally high levels of SPD of all HRV

bands, especially VLF, relative SPD of beta-rhythm in F3, F4 and F7 loci, a pronounced rightward shift of the lateralization of theta rhythm as well as abnormally high Energy level of first, fifth and sixth *virtual* Chakras, registered by GDV method [Flyunt VR et al., 2017; Babelyuk VY et., 2023]. That is, there can be no talk of any artifact regarding FEUA. It is important that after a week of using Naftussya bioactive water (and maybe spontaneously), both FEUA and the listed variables were significantly or even completely normalized.

Further, following the adopted algorithm, profiles (Fig. 4) and patterns (Fig. 5) of accompanied changes in parameters of neuro-endocrine-immune complex and metabolism at various clusters of changes were created (Fig. 4).

Of the variables selected by the discriminant analysis (forward stepwise method) [Klecka WR, 1989], only 27 were included in the model (Tables 2 and 3). Among them, in addition to UA Clearance, UA urine Concentration and Excretion by definition, there were 9 other metabolic variables, 9 EEG, 2 HRV, 2 Immune variables, as well as Cortisol and di-

Fig. 4. Profiles of accompanied changes in parameters of neuro-endocrine-immune complex and metabolism at clusters of changes in uric acid clearance & fractional excretion (see also Table 6)

Fig. 5. Patterns of accompanied changes in parameters of neuro-endocrine-immune complex and metabolism at clusters of changes in uric acid clearance & fractional excretion. Under each pattern the number of variables is indicated

Table 2

Summary of discriminant function analysis Variables changes in which currently in the model
 Step 27, N of vars in model: 27; Grouping: 5 grp; Wilks' Λ : 0,00004; appr. F (108) = 6,1; $p < 10^{-6}$

Changes in Variables currently in the model (Mean \pm SE)	Clusters of changes in Uric Acid Clearance&Fractional Excretion (Men/Women)					Parameters of Wilks' Statistics				
	C0 FE- (7/1)	C2+ FE- (8/1)	C+ FE0 (12/3)	C2- FE- (3/3)	C- FE2- (4/2)	Wilks $\Lambda \cdot 10^{-3}$	Partial Λ	F-remove (4,13)	p-level	Tolerance
Uric Acid Clearance, mL/min	0,13	4,98	1,29	-8,54	-2,83	0,067	0,535	2,830	0,069	0,113
Uric Acid Urine, mM/L	-0,31	0,19	-0,10	-0,72	-2,33	0,168	0,214	11,95	10 ⁻⁴	0,054
Uricosuria, mM/24 h	0,14	2,32	0,62	-2,77	-1,05	0,087	0,413	4,623	0,015	0,049
Creatininuria, mM/24h	2,56	4,20	1,69	-3,60	0,04	0,048	0,751	1,075	0,408	0,342
Urea Excretion, mM/24h	52	301	84	-196	46	0,099	0,364	5,683	0,007	0,085
Phosphate Excretion, mM/24h	7,1	15,9	16,9	0,2	5,6	0,060	0,602	2,149	0,132	0,157
Potassium Excretion, mM/24h	7,4	29,8	-0,9	-18,5	-3,1	0,137	0,262	9,139	0,001	0,096
Magnesium Excretion, mM/24h	-0,40	1,78	0,99	-0,88	0,80	0,058	0,625	1,950	0,162	0,312
Glucose, mM/L	-0,47	-0,37	0,00	0,22	0,71	0,080	0,449	3,990	0,025	0,166
Diene conjugates, E ²³² /mL	-0,03	0,11	0,03	-0,08	-0,07	0,127	0,283	8,249	0,002	0,043
Catalase, μ M/L-h	18	-10	-17	27	13	0,178	0,202	12,82	10 ⁻⁴	0,043
C-Reactive Protein, μ g/L	-0,34	-0,42	-0,25	-0,41	0,42	0,093	0,388	5,118	0,011	0,162
Frequency- θ , Hz	-0,75	0,83	-0,75	0,80	0,67	0,126	0,286	8,104	0,002	0,089
Laterality- θ , %	1	-69	-13	14	2	0,139	0,258	9,331	0,001	0,072
SPD O1- θ , %	1,1	1,0	2,1	-5,3	1,8	0,076	0,470	3,662	0,033	0,189
SPD C3- β , %	-8,7	10,9	3,6	-6,2	-6,1	0,073	0,494	3,325	0,044	0,016
SPD C4- β , %	-10,2	5,9	2,8	7,1	5,6	0,069	0,525	2,944	0,062	0,037
SPD P4- β , %	-7,9	5,2	4,4	-13,3	-7,6	0,122	0,294	7,820	0,002	0,023
SPD C4- α , %	-6,6	9,8	-5,8	7,0	5,8	0,061	0,591	2,247	0,120	0,119
SPD C3- δ , %	13,2	-23,6	1,7	0,8	3,1	0,047	0,763	1,010	0,437	0,056
SPD T3 Entropy	-0,01	0,11	-0,13	-0,12	0,03	0,048	0,748	1,096	0,399	0,235
(VLF+LF)/HF HRV Ratio	-2,33	-3,01	-1,22	-10,9	1,38	0,058	0,622	1,975	0,158	0,110
LF/HF HRV Ratio	0,04	0,59	-0,61	-7,62	0,40	0,056	0,644	1,800	0,189	0,149
BP diastolic, mmHg	0,2	6,6	0,2	-5,2	-0,2	0,117	0,306	7,370	0,003	0,130
Cortisol, nM/L	-128	22	94	156	167	0,312	0,115	24,92	10 ⁻⁵	0,073
CD4 ⁺ T-helper Lymphocytes, %	-1,25	3,22	2,60	-2,00	1,33	0,093	0,385	5,191	0,010	0,220
CIC serum, units	4,5	7,3	-8,8	6,0	13,0	0,050	0,726	1,229	0,346	0,301

Table 3

Summary of Stepwise Analysis for Variables, ranked by criterion Lambda

Variables currently in the model	F to enter	p-level	Λ	F-value	p-value
Uric Acid Clearance, mL/min	69,21	10 ⁻⁶	0,12347	69,21	10 ⁻⁶
SPD T3 Entropy	3,321	0,020	0,09149	21,91	10 ⁻⁶
Uric Acid Urine, mM/L	2,807	0,039	0,07019	14,15	10 ⁻⁶
SPD C4- α , %	2,497	0,060	0,05495	10,96	10 ⁻⁶
Cortisol, nM/L	3,245	0,023	0,04008	9,583	10 ⁻⁶
LF/HF HRV Ratio	2,116	0,100	0,03209	8,388	10 ⁻⁶
SPD P4- β , %	1,837	0,145	0,02625	7,502	10 ⁻⁶
Frequency- θ , Hz	2,494	0,062	0,02001	7,058	10 ⁻⁶
Potassium Excretion, mM/24h	2,357	0,075	0,01534	6,709	10 ⁻⁶
SPD O1- θ , %	1,890	0,138	0,01225	6,338	10 ⁻⁶
Catalase, μ M/L-h	1,980	0,124	0,00963	6,071	10 ⁻⁶
C-Reactive Protein, μ g/L	1,960	0,128	0,00752	5,859	10 ⁻⁶
Laterality- θ , %	1,675	0,185	0,00602	5,628	10 ⁻⁶
BP diastolic, mmHg	3,594	0,018	0,00388	5,844	10 ⁻⁶
Phosphate Excretion, mM/24h	3,454	0,022	0,00250	6,058	10 ⁻⁶
CIC serum, units	2,091	0,113	0,00185	5,996	10 ⁻⁶
Urea Excretion, mM/24h	3,171	0,033	0,00119	6,204	10 ⁻⁶
Uricosuria, mM/24 h	2,155	0,108	0,00086	6,200	10 ⁻⁶
SPD C3- δ , %	1,845	0,158	0,00063	6,139	10 ⁻⁶
CD4 ⁺ T-helper Lymphocytes, %	1,590	0,216	0,00048	6,030	10 ⁻⁶
Diene conjugates, E ²³² /mL	1,347	0,289	0,00038	5,874	10 ⁻⁶
SPD C4- β , %	2,997	0,047	0,00023	6,162	10 ⁻⁶
Magnesium Excretion, mM/24h	2,158	0,118	0,00015	6,264	10 ⁻⁶
Glucose, mM/L	1,337	0,299	0,00011	6,136	10 ⁻⁶
SPD C3- β , %	2,133	0,127	0,00007	6,271	10 ⁻⁶
(VLF+LF)/HF HRV Ratio	1,724	0,201	0,00005	6,298	10 ⁻⁶
Creatininuria, mM/24h	1,075	0,408	0,00004	6,106	10 ⁻⁶

astolic BP.

Instead, 11 variables (Table 4), primarily UAFE, despite their obvious discriminative ability, were left out of the model, which, as shown

in previous studies by our group, is due to the duplication/excess of discriminative information contained in these variables.

Next, the 27-dimensional space of discriminant variables transforms into 4-dimensional space of a canonical roots. For Root 1 $r^* = 0,988$ (Wilks' $\Lambda = 0,00004$; $\chi^2_{(108)} = 276$; $p < 10^{-6}$), for Root 2 $r^* = 0,970$ (Wilks' $\Lambda = 0,0016$; $\chi^2_{(78)} = 175$; $p < 10^{-6}$), for Root 3 $r^* = 0,942$ (Wilks' $\Lambda = 0,027$; $\chi^2_{(50)} = 98$; $p < 10^{-4}$), and for Root 4 $r^* = 0,874$ (Wilks' $\Lambda = 0,237$; $\chi^2_{(24)} = 39$; $p = 0,028$). The first root contains 60,9 % of discriminative opportunities, the second 23,1 %, the third 11,4 %, and the last 4,6 % only, therefore will be ignored in the future.

Table 5 presents raw and standardized coefficients for discriminant variables, which are used for the calculation of the discriminant root values for each person, which enables the visualization of each patient in the information space of the roots (Fig. 6).

The localization in the extreme right zone of the axis of the first root of the members of the **C-FE2-** cluster reflects the maximum decrease in them, together with FEUA and UA Urine, SPD of LF band HRV, asymmetry of theta-rhythm and Cholecystokinetics, on the one hand, in combination with the maximum increase in the serum level of C-RP, CIC, Glucose and Cortisol for the sample — on the other hand (Fig. 3 and Table 6).

The localization in the extreme lower zone of the axis of the second root of the members of the **C2-FE-** cluster reflects the maximum decrease in them, together with UA Clearance and Excretion, firstly, Diuresis and

Standardized and Raw Coefficients and Constants for Variables

Variables currently in the model	Coefficients			Standardized			Raw		
	Root 1	Root 2	Root 3	Root 1	Root 2	Root 3	Root 1	Root 2	Root 3
Uric Acid Clearance, mL/min	-1,271	1,502	0,686	-0,783	0,925	0,422			
SPD T3 Entropy	0,331	0,279	-0,071	2,191	1,842	-0,469			
Uric Acid Urine, mM/L	-2,631	-0,736	2,208	-2,173	-0,608	1,824			
SPD C4-α, %	1,754	0,032	-0,484	0,166	0,003	-0,046			
Cortisol, nM/L	3,089	0,576	-1,640	0,013	0,002	-0,007			
LF/HF HRV Ratio	-0,467	1,461	-0,427	-0,089	0,277	-0,081			
SPD P4-β, %	-4,814	1,065	2,630	-0,462	0,102	0,253			
Frequency-θ, Hz	1,852	2,166	0,378	1,391	1,626	0,284			
Potassium Excretion, mM/24h	-2,627	-0,373	0,889	-0,055	-0,008	0,019			
SPD O1-θ, %	1,254	-0,234	-0,633	0,314	-0,059	-0,158			
Catalase, μM/L-h	-1,095	4,037	1,563	-0,023	0,084	0,032			
C-Reactive Protein, μg/L	0,052	1,930	0,463	0,057	2,121	0,509			
Laterality-θ, %	2,416	1,686	-0,961	0,053	0,037	-0,021			
BP diastolic, mmHg	1,891	1,217	-0,699	0,221	0,142	-0,082			
Phosphate Excretion, mM/24h	-1,243	-0,646	0,189	-0,074	-0,038	0,011			
CIC serum, units	0,246	0,844	0,447	0,012	0,042	0,022			
Urea Excretion, mM/24h	-1,729	-0,348	1,296	-0,012	-0,002	0,009			
Uricosuria, mM/24 h	1,900	-0,721	-2,777	2,593	-0,984	-3,790			
SPD C3-δ, %	1,301	-1,640	-0,094	0,062	-0,078	-0,004			
CD4 ⁺ T-helper Lymphocytes, %	1,313	-0,646	-0,898	0,264	-0,130	-0,181			
Diene conjugates, E ²³² /mL	-2,778	2,223	2,142	-22,60	18,08	17,42			
SPD C4-β, %	2,002	-0,883	-2,844	0,159	-0,070	-0,226			
Magnesium Excretion, mM/24h	0,496	-0,863	-0,531	0,264	-0,458	-0,282			
Glucose, mM/L	1,289	-0,529	-1,124	1,176	-0,483	-1,025			
SPD C3-β, %	3,634	-3,623	-1,935	0,277	-0,276	-0,148			
(VLF+LF)/HF HRV Ratio	-0,861	0,602	1,279	-0,084	0,059	0,125			
Creatininuria, mM/24h	0,163	0,629	0,527	0,049	0,190	0,159			
			Constants	-1,469	1,483	1,713			
			Eigenvalues	42,36	16,04	7,909			
			Cumulative proportions	0,609	0,840	0,954			

Table 5

diastolic BP, and blood level of CD4⁺ Th-lymphocytes. Secondly, this cluster differs from the others in the maximum decrease in LF/HF and (VLF+LF)/HF ratios of HRV, SPD of theta-rhythm in O1 locus and beta-rhythm in P4 locus as well as in systolic BP and serum level of Diene conjugates, combined with the maximal increase in the activity of both antioxidant enzymes, as well as the rightward shift of the lateralization of theta rhythm.

The delimitation of **COFE-** and **C2+FE-** clusters occurs along the third root axis according to the polar changes in the frequency of theta rhythm and SPD of beta rhythm in C4 and C3 loci, on the one hand, as well as SPD of delta rhythm in C3 and C4 loci — on the other hand.

In general, in the information space of the three discriminant roots, all 5 clusters are very clearly delimited, which is documented by the calculation of Mahalanobis distances (Table 7).

The same discriminant parameters, by using the coefficients and constants of the classification functions (Table 8), allow identifying the belonging of one or another person to one or another cluster with 100 % accuracy (Table 9).

Discussion

The results obtained are the first systematic description of the polyvariance of the responses of clearance and fractional excretion of uric acid to balneotherapy in patients with chronic pyelonephritis in the remission phase. The identification of five qualitatively distinct clusters confirms the conceptual position of the authors regarding the inadmissibility of averaging group effects of therapeutic intervention with-

Correlations Variables-Canonical Roots, Means of Roots and Z-scores of Variables

Variables currently in the model	Correlations Variables-Roots			C0	C2+	C+	C2-	C-
	R 1	R 2	R 3	FE- (7/1)	FE- (8/1)	FE0 (12/3)	FE- (3/3)	FE2- (4/2)
Root 1 (60,9 %)				-5,5	-4,6	-2,1	9,3	10,2
FE UA				-1,33 ± 0,60	-0,74 ± 0,48	-0,06 ± 0,37	-1,66 ± 0,45	-4,78 ± 4,06
UA Urine	-0,09	-0,07	-0,01	-0,59 ± 0,35	0,35 ± 0,53	-0,19 ± 0,20	-1,34 ± 0,61	-4,34 ± 2,35
SPD LF HRV				1,16 ± 1,05	-0,14 ± 0,76	0,77 ± 0,52	-1,28 ± 1,63	-2,35 ± 1,88
Asymmetry-θ				0,09 ± 0,67	0,01 ± 0,39	0,44 ± 0,36	-0,39 ± 0,21	-1,81 ± 0,71
CCK				1,37 ± 0,89	1,58 ± 0,45	1,79 ± 0,45	-0,60 ± 0,96	-1,17 ± 0,31
C-RP	0,02	0,05	-0,05	-0,48 ± 0,21	-0,59 ± 0,46	-0,36 ± 0,34	-0,57 ± 0,56	0,59 ± 0,27
CIC serum	0,03	0,09	0,04	0,26 ± 0,22	0,42 ± 0,28	-0,50 ± 0,40	0,34 ± 0,43	0,74 ± 0,34
Glucose	0,04	-0,02	-0,08	-0,62 ± 0,61	-0,49 ± 0,40	-0,01 ± 0,43	0,30 ± 0,26	0,94 ± 0,70
Cortisol	0,06	-0,04	-0,09	-1,05 ± 0,70	0,18 ± 0,48	0,81 ± 0,56	1,34 ± 0,78	1,48 ± 0,80
Root 2 (23,1%)				2,28	3,35	-3,87	-3,76	5,37
UA Clearance	-0,34	0,18	-0,48	0,09 ± 0,21	3,70 ± 0,41	0,95 ± 0,13	-6,11 ± 0,99	-2,05 ± 0,38
Uricosuria	-0,28	0,14	-0,41	0,18 ± 0,16	3,10 ± 0,44	0,83 ± 0,17	-3,69 ± 0,58	-1,40 ± 0,44
Urea Excretion	-0,11	0,12	-0,22	0,61 ± 0,40	3,54 ± 0,66	0,98 ± 0,47	-2,30 ± 0,73	0,54 ± 0,64
Diuresis				0,64 ± 0,20	2,41 ± 0,25	1,20 ± 0,22	-1,76 ± 0,55	0,76 ± 0,31
Chloride Excr				-1,31 ± 1,54	1,99 ± 0,95	-0,65 ± 0,96	-1,80 ± 1,84	1,54 ± 1,27
Sodium Excret				-1,20 ± 1,18	1,52 ± 0,73	-0,64 ± 0,71	-1,73 ± 1,52	1,17 ± 0,70
Creatininuria	-0,10	0,08	-0,09	0,78 ± 0,58	1,27 ± 0,22	0,51 ± 0,20	-1,09 ± 0,21	0,01 ± 0,48
SPD T3 Entrop	-0,01	0,12	-0,02	-0,09 ± 0,41	1,00 ± 0,71	-1,17 ± 0,35	-1,03 ± 0,75	0,26 ± 0,22
Potassium Excr	-0,04	0,05	-0,04	0,42 ± 0,50	1,70 ± 0,71	-0,05 ± 0,95	-1,06 ± 0,72	-0,17 ± 1,03
Magnesium Ex	-0,03	0,03	-0,16	-0,38 ± 0,64	1,69 ± 0,35	0,94 ± 0,49	-0,84 ± 0,96	0,76 ± 0,71
BP diastolic	-0,04	0,06	-0,08	0,04 ± 0,33	1,00 ± 0,52	0,03 ± 0,33	-0,80 ± 0,48	-0,03 ± 0,62
CD4 ⁺ T-help	-0,02	0,00	-0,14	-0,39 ± 0,44	0,99 ± 0,69	0,80 ± 0,42	-0,62 ± 0,26	0,41 ± 0,48
Phosphate Excr	-0,04	-0,02	-0,10	0,95 ± 0,74	2,15 ± 0,55	2,29 ± 0,74	0,02 ± 0,89	0,76 ± 0,60
LF/HF HRV	-0,05	0,07	-0,08	0,02 ± 1,00	0,33 ± 0,95	-0,31 ± 0,47	-3,67 ± 1,66	0,18 ± 0,49
(VLF+LF)/HF	-0,02	0,04	-0,06	-0,64 ± 0,88	-0,67 ± 0,83	-0,37 ± 0,67	-2,81 ± 0,97	0,35 ± 1,10
SPD O1-θ r	-0,04	0,04	-0,09	0,23 ± 0,45	0,20 ± 0,74	0,43 ± 0,22	-1,11 ± 0,39	0,38 ± 0,35
SPD P4-β r	-0,06	-0,03	-0,15	-0,69 ± 0,37	0,45 ± 0,46	0,39 ± 0,15	-1,16 ± 0,53	-0,66 ± 0,37
BP systolic				-0,40 ± 0,14	0,40 ± 0,31	0,13 ± 0,21	-0,49 ± 0,27	-0,15 ± 0,37
Diene conjugate	-0,05	0,05	-0,09	-0,06 ± 0,05	0,21 ± 0,09	0,06 ± 0,06	-0,15 ± 0,04	-0,13 ± 0,13
Laterality-θ	0,04	-0,03	0,10	0,04 ± 0,19	-1,78 ± 0,70	-0,33 ± 0,29	0,36 ± 0,15	0,06 ± 0,60
SOD Erythro				0,50 ± 0,22	-0,59 ± 0,38	0,01 ± 0,22	0,73 ± 0,22	0,56 ± 0,64
Catalase Serum	0,02	0,05	0,06	0,05 ± 0,23	0,07 ± 0,32	-0,29 ± 0,20	0,83 ± 0,27	0,23 ± 0,37
Root 3 (11,4 %)				4,56	-2,18	-1,62	2,76	-1,53
SPD C4-β r	-0,03	0,01	-0,15	-0,98 ± 0,54	1,53 ± 0,42	0,19 ± 0,25	-0,59 ± 0,64	-0,32 ± 0,58
SPD C3-β r	-0,04	-0,02	-0,12	-0,81 ± 0,54	1,01 ± 0,55	0,33 ± 0,26	-0,58 ± 0,66	-0,57 ± 0,52
Frequency-θ	0,05	0,06	-0,03	-0,57 ± 0,58	0,64 ± 0,34	-0,57 ± 0,29	0,61 ± 0,26	0,51 ± 0,36
SPD C4-α r	0,04	0,07	-0,05	-0,44 ± 0,17	0,65 ± 0,22	-0,38 ± 0,24	0,46 ± 0,25	0,39 ± 0,34
SPD C3-δ r	0,01	-0,02	0,10	0,78 ± 0,51	-1,40 ± 0,45	0,10 ± 0,30	0,04 ± 0,64	0,18 ± 0,62
SPD C4-δ r				1,07 ± 0,47	-1,39 ± 0,36	0,34 ± 0,30	-0,12 ± 0,55	-0,23 ± 0,72
SPD C4-δ a				1,05 ± 0,53	-4,36 ± 1,58	1,12 ± 0,97	0,81 ± 1,05	-0,73 ± 0,98

Table 6

Excretion of Urea, Chloride, Sodium, Creatinine, Potassium, Magnesium, and Phosphate as well as Entropy of SPD in T3 locus EEG,

regarding the inadmissibility of averaging group effects of therapeutic intervention with-

Table 7
 Squared Mahalanobis Distances between Clusters of changes (above diagonal) and F-values (df = 27,1) and p-levels (below diagonal)

Clusters of changes	C2- FE-	C2+ FE-	C- FE2-	C+ FE0	C0 FE-
C2-FE- (3/3)	0	269	120	161	272
C2+FE- (8/1)	12,0 10 ⁻⁶	0	242	70	58
C-FE2- (4/2)	4,45 0,003	10,7 10 ⁻⁵	0	238	296
C+FE0 (12/3)	8,54 10 ⁻⁴	4,86 0,002	12,6 10 ⁻³	0	88
C0FE- (7/1)	11,5 10 ⁻⁴	3,05 0,019	12,5 10 ⁻³	5,66 0,001	0

Table 8
 Coefficients and Constants for Classification Functions for Clusters

Clusters of changes in Uric Acid Clearance&Fractional Excretion	C2- FE-	C2+ FE-	C- FE2-	C+ FE0	C0 FE-
Variables currently in the model	p =,136	p =,205	p =,136	p =,341	p =,182
Uric Acid Clearance, mL/min	-13,57	1,840	-7,422	-6,410	4,584
SPD T3 Entropy	30,90	15,41	21,80	-16,56	-15,20
Uric Acid Urine, mM/L	-13,61	3,310	-35,68	-2,190	12,92
SPD C4-α, %	1,649	-0,417	2,238	0,129	-0,710
Cortisol, nM/L	0,125	-0,009	0,186	-0,001	-0,076
LF/HF HRV Ratio	-2,471	1,135	0,220	-1,223	0,289
SPD P4-β, %	-5,499	0,436	-5,738	-1,071	2,706
Frequency-θ, Hz	6,681	-2,578	20,33	-11,62	-4,619
Potassium Excretion, mM/24h	-0,504	0,119	-0,739	0,019	0,277
SPD O1-θ, %	3,072	-0,928	4,606	1,090	-1,347
Catalase, μM/L-h	-0,627	0,124	-0,046	-0,539	0,255
C-Reactive Protein, μg/L	-9,045	2,714	6,778	-13,30	2,721
Laterality-θ, %	0,284	-0,109	0,850	-0,167	-0,254
BP diastolic, mmHg	1,651	-0,021	3,430	-0,591	-0,980
Phosphate Excretion, mM/24h	-0,326	0,372	-1,008	0,293	0,384
CIC serum, units	-0,074	-0,056	0,244	-0,304	0,052
Urea Excretion, mM/24h	-0,060	0,044	-0,187	-0,009	0,072
Uricosuria, mM/24 h	23,67	-0,711	40,28	16,45	-22,06
SPD C3-δ, %	1,052	-0,342	0,430	0,386	-0,333
CD4 ⁺ T-helper Lymphocytes, %	3,404	-0,317	3,280	1,232	-1,598
Diene conjugates, E ²³² /mL	-292,3	65,24	-245,5	-131,4	165,6
SPD C4-β, %	1,581	-0,016	2,420	1,061	-1,319
Magnesium Excretion, mM/24h	4,541	-1,003	2,058	3,021	-2,456
Glucose, mM/L	15,66	0,865	14,23	4,770	-8,546
SPD C3-β, %	4,681	-0,426	2,467	1,729	-1,828
(VLF+LF)/HF HRV Ratio	-1,427	-0,450	-1,051	-0,655	0,758
Creatininuria, mM/24h	-0,435	-0,551	1,075	-1,378	0,600
Constants	-80,63	-21,68	-84,99	-22,46	-15,66

Table 9

Classification Matrix

Group	Rows: Observed classifications Columns: Predicted classifications					
	Percent Correct	C2-FE- p=,13636	C2+FE- p=,20455	C-FE2- p=,13636	C+FE0 p=,34091	C0FE- p=,18182
C2-FE-	100	6	0	0	0	0
C2+FE-	100	0	9	0	0	0
C-FE2-	100	0	0	6	0	0
C+FE0	100	0	0	0	15	0
C0FE-	100	0	0	0	0	8
Total	100	6	9	6	15	8

out taking into account individual variability of response.

The most common cluster C+FE0 (34.5 % of patients) is characterized by a moderate increase in clearance in the absence of significant changes in fractional excretion. From a pathophysiological point of view, this indicates a predominantly glomerular mechanism of increased uraturia — an increase in glomerular filtration with relatively stable tubular transport. This option is the most favorable clinically.

Cluster C2+FE" (20.5 %) demonstrates the most pronounced uraturic response — a significant increase in clearance combined with increased excretion of most electrolytes

and urea. The characteristic increase in diastolic blood pressure and an increase in the relative SBP of the beta rhythm in the central EEG loci may reflect activation of the sympatho-adrenal system.

Cluster C0FE" (18.2 %) is interesting pathophysiologically: the absence of significant changes in clearance with a moderate decrease in fractional excretion may indicate a predominantly tubular mechanism — increased reabsorption of urate in the proximal tubules with relatively stable glomerular filtration.

Clusters C2"FE" and C"FE2" (13.6 % each) represent potentially unfavorable reaction variants. Cluster C2"FE" is characterized by the maximum decrease in HRV indices LF/HF and (VLF+LF)/HF, which indicates a pronounced suppression of sympathetic tone. Cluster C"FE2" is characterized by an increase in the levels of C-

Fig. 6. Scattering of individual values of the discriminant roots of patients from different clusters of changes in uric acid clearance&fractional excretion (see also Fig. 4)

reactive protein and CIC, which may indicate the activation of the inflammatory process.

An important theoretical contribution is the confirmation of the concept of the neuro-endocrine-immune complex as an integrative system for the regulation of renal functions. The inclusion of EEG (9 variables), HRV (2), immunological (2) parameters in the discriminant model, along with metabolic and hormonal parameters, indicates that the renal response to balneotherapy is a systemic response of the entire neuro-endocrine-immune complex.

Cortisol was the most powerful discriminant in the model, emphasizing the central role of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis in regulating the renal response to balneotherapy.

Study limitations: relatively small sample size (44 patients) with uneven distribution across clusters (6–15 patients); lack of a control group; single-center design; 100 % classification accuracy requires confirmation by cross-validation; gender imbalance (34 men and 10 women).

Despite these limitations, the identified five clusters of reactions can serve as the basis for developing an algorithm for personalized balneotherapy prescription and timely detection of adverse response options for correction of treatment tactics.

Conclusion

1. In patients with chronic pyelonephritis in the remission phase, the response to the standard course of balneotherapy at the Truskavets resort is multivariate — the method of iterative k-means clustering revealed five qualitatively distinct clusters of changes in clearance and fractional excretion of uric acid, which fundamentally differ in direction, magnitude, and pathophysiological content of the reactions.
2. Uric acid clearance and fractional excretion respond to balneotherapy factors independently of each other — the overall correlation between their changes is weak, reflecting the relative autonomy of glomerular filtration and tubular transport of urate.

3. The most common response is a moderate increase in clearance in the absence of significant changes in fractional excretion (cluster C+FE0, 34.5 %), accompanied by an increase in diuresis, phosphate excretion, and antioxidant enzyme activity.
4. A significant increase in clearance combined with a moderate decrease in fractional excretion (cluster C2+FE", 20.5 %) is accompanied by a maximum increase in diuresis and excretion of urea, chlorides, sodium, potassium, magnesium, and phosphates, as well as normalization of EEG entropy in the temporal locus.
5. A significant decrease in clearance combined with a significant decrease in fractional excretion (cluster C"FE2", 13.6 %) is characterized by a maximum increase in the levels of C-reactive protein, CIC, glucose, and cortisol, indicating activation of the stress response and inflammatory process.
6. Each of the five clusters is accompanied by a specific pattern of changes in the parameters of the neuro-endocrine-immune complex and metabolism, which includes 9 EEG parameters, 2 HRV parameters, 2 immunological parameters, 9 metabolic parameters, as well as cortisol and diastolic blood pressure.
7. Discriminant analysis using 27 variables allows identifying each patient's belonging to the corresponding cluster with 100 % accuracy; the first three canonical roots explain 60.9 %, 23.1 %, and 11.4 % of the discriminant possibilities.
8. The unique clinical case of patient Dr with abnormally high FEUA (87.5 %), which completely normalized after a course of taking Naftusya bioactive water, demonstrates the powerful regulatory potential of balneotherapy and emphasizes the importance of preserving "outlier" values in the analysis.
9. Among the parameters of the neuro-endocrine-immune complex, the leading regulatory role is played by the indicators of the autonomic nervous system (SPD LF HRV) and the central nervous system

(EEG), while changes in most metabolic indicators are mainly consequential.

10. The results obtained justify the need to transition from an averaged group to an individualized cluster approach when prescribing and assessing the effectiveness of balneotherapy in patients with chronic pyelonephritis.

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Accordance To Ethics Standards

Tests in patients are conducted in accordance with positions of Helsinki Declaration 1975, revised and complemented in 2002, and directive of National Committee on ethics of scientific researches. During realization of tests from all participants the informed consent is got and used all measures for providing of anonymity of participants.

References

- Aldenderfer MS & Blashfield RK. Cluster analysis (Second printing, 1985) [transl. from English in Russian]. In: Factor, Discriminant and Cluster Analysis. Moskva. Finansy i Statistika; 1989: 139-214.
- Andreyeva LI, Kozhemyakin LA, Kishkun AA. Modification of the method for determining the lipid peroxide in the test with thiobarbituric acid [in Russian]. *Laboratornoye Delo*. 1988; 11: 41-43.
- Anscombe FJ. Graphs in Statistical Analysis. *American Statistician*. 1973; 27: 17-21.
- Babelyuk VY, Popovych IL, Gozhenko AI, Dubkova GI, Kozyavkina OV, Korolyshyn TA, Babelyuk NV, Kovbanyuk MM, Fihura OA, Dobrovolskyi YG, Zukow W, Yanchij RI. Gas Discharge Visualization (Electrophotonic Imaging, Kirlianography). Theoretical and Applied Aspects. Odessa Feniks; 2023: 186. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7535880>
- Baevsky R. & Chernikova A. Heart rate variability analysis: physiological foundations and main methods. *Cardiometry*. 2017; 10: 66-76. doi: 10.12710/CARDIOMETRY.2017.10.6676
- Berntson GG, Bigger JT jr, Eckberg DL, Grossman P, Kaufman PG, Malik M, Nagaraja HN, Porges SW, Saul JP, Stone PH, Van der Molen MW. Heart Rate Variability: Origines, methods, and interpretive caveats. *Psychophysiology*. 1997; 34: 623-648. doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-8986.1997.tb02140.x
- Biletsky SV & Gozhenko AI. Hypoxic-hypercapnic training in cardiology. Chernivtsi: 2007.
- Chatterjee S. & Firat A. Generating Data with Identical Statistics but Dissimilar Graphics: A Follow up to the Anscombe Dataset. *American Statistician*. 2007; 61 (3): 248-254. doi: 10.1198/000313007X220057
- Chebanienko OI, Flyunt IS, Popovych IL, Balanovskyi VP, Lakhin PV. Water Naftussya and Water-salt Exchange [in Ukrainian]. Kyiv: Naukova dumka; 1997: 141.
- Dubinina YY, Yefimova LF, Sofronova LN, Geronimus AL. Comparative analysis of the activity of superoxide dismutase and catalase of erythrocytes and whole blood from newborn children with chronic hypoxia [in Russian]. *Laboratornoye Delo*. 1988; 8: 16-19.
- Flyunt VR, Flyunt I-SS, Fil' VM, Kovbasnyuk MM, Hryvna R, Popel SL, Zukow W. Relationships between caused by drinking of bioactive water Naftussya changes in urine lithogenicity and neuro-humoral-immune factors in humans with their abnormalities. *Journal of Education, Health and Sport*. 2017; 7 (3): 11-30.
- Gavrilov VB, Mishkorudnaya MI. Spectrophotometric determination of plasma levels of lipid hydroperoxides [in Russian]. *Laboratornoye Delo*. 1983; 3: 33-36.
- Goryachkovskiy AM. *Clinical Biochemistry* [in Russian]. Odessa: Astroprint; 1998: 608.
- Gozhenko AI. Functional-metabolic continuum [in Russian]. *Journal of NAMS of Ukraine*. 2016; 22 (1): 3-8.
- Gozhenko AI, Korda MM, Popadynets OO, Popovych IL. Entropy, Harmony, Synchronization and Their Neuro-Endocrine-Immune Correlates [in Ukrainian]. Odessa Feniks; 2021: 232.
- Gozhenko, A, Zantaraia, T, Zukow, W. „Falling values”: artifacts or source of unique information? Drastically low electrical conductivity of acupuncture points is accompanied by significant deviations of EEG, HRV, immunity, metabolism and GDV parameters. *Quality in Sport*. 2024; 17: 51006. <https://dx.doi.org/10.12775/QS.2024.17.004>
- Gozhenko AI, Ishchenko VS. Neuro-endocrine regulation of the clearance of uric acid. *VA=8: <>@AL:>W <548F8=8*. 2025; 1 (106): 41-51.
- Heart Rate Variability. Standards of Measurement, Physiological Interpretation, and Clinical Use. Task Force of ESC and NASPE. *Circulation*. 1996; 93 (5): 1043-1065. doi: 10.1161/01.CIR.93.5.1043
- Hozhenko AI, Kravchuk AV, Nikitenko OP, Moskalenko OM, Sirman VM. Funktsional'nyi nyrkovyi rezerv. Functional renal reserve [in Ukrainian]. Odessa: Feniks; 2015: 180.
- Hyndman D, Liu S, Miner JN. Urate Handling in the Human Body. *Curr Rheumatol Rep*. 2016; 18 (6): 34. doi: 10.1007/s11926-016-0587-7.

21. Ishchenko VS, Anchev AS, Ivanov DD, Zukow W. Peculiarities of metabolic and autonomic-endocrine accompaniments of urate-losing/retaining kidneys. *Quality in Sport*. 2024; 16: 51441-51441. doi.org/10.12775/QS.2024.16.51441
22. Ishchenko VS, Anchev AS. Peculiarities of neuro-endocrine-immune accompaniments of urate-losing/retaining kidneys. *Actual Problems of Transport Medicine*. 2024; 4 (78): 77-85.
23. Klecka WR. Discriminant Analysis [trans. from English in Russian] (Seventh Printing, 1986). In: Factor, Discriminant and Cluster Analysis. Moskva: Finansy i Statistika; 1989: 78-138.
24. Korda MM, Gozhenko AI, Popovych IL, Klishch IM, Bombushkar IS, Korda IV, Badiuk NS, Zukow WA, Smaglyi VS. Neurotropic, Hormonal and Immunotropic Activity of Uric Acid. Monograph. Ternopil': Ukrmedknyha; 2024: 206. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990426
25. Korolyuk MA, Ivanova MI, Mayorova IG, Tokarev VYe. The method for determining the activity of catalase [in Russian]. *Laboratornoye Delo*. 1988; 1: 16-19.
26. Kulchynskiy AB, Kovbasnyuk MM, Korolyshyn TA, Kyjenko VM, Zukow W, Popovych IL. Neuro-immune relationships at patients with chronic pyelonephrite and cholecystite. Communication 2. Correlations between parameters EEG, HRV and Phagocytosis. *Journal of Education, Health and Sport*. 2016; 6 (10): 377-401. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163221
27. Lapovets LYe & Lutsyk BD. Handbook of Laboratory Immunology [in Ukrainian]. Lviv; 2004: 173.
28. Lukovych YuS, Popovych AI, Kovbasnyuk MM, Korolyshyn TA, Barylyak LG, Popovych IL. Neuroendocrine and immune support of the diuretic effect of balneotherapy at the Truskavets resort [in Ukrainian]. *Kidneys*. 2015; 2 (12): 7-14.
29. Makarenko YeV. A comprehensive definition of the activity of superoxide dismutase and glutathione reductase in red blood cells in patients with chronic liver disease [in Russian]. *Laboratornoye Delo*. 1988; 11: 48-50.
30. Marfiyan OM, Korolyshyn TA, Barylyak LG, Kovbasnyuk MM, Yavors'kyi OV, Zukow W, Popovych IL. Neuroendocrine-immune and metabolic accompaniments of cholecystokinetic effects of balneotherapy on spa Truskavets'. *Journal of Education, Health and Sport*. 2015; 5 (5): 21-30.
31. Park JH, Jo YI, Lee JH. Renal effects of uric acid: hyperuricemia and hypouricemia. *Korean J Intern Med*. 2020; 35 (6): 1291-1304. doi: 10.3904/kjim.2020.410.
32. Perez-Ruiz F, Calabozo M, Erauskin GG, Ruibal A, Herrero-Beites AM. Renal underexcretion of uric acid is present in patients with apparent high urinary uric acid output. *Arthritis Rheum*. 2002; 47 (6): 610-613. doi: 10.1002/art.10792.
33. Perez-Gomez MV, Bartsch LA, Castillo-Rodriguez E, Fernandez-Prado R, Kanbay M, Ortiz A. Potential dangers of serum urate-lowering therapy. *Am J Med*. 2019; 132: 457-467. doi: 10.1016/j.amjmed.2018.12.010.
34. Popadynets O, Gozhenko A, Badyuk N, et al. Interpersonal differences caused by adaptogen changes in entropies of EEG, HRV, immunocytogram, and leukocytogram. *Journal of Physical Education and Sport*. 2020; 20 (Suppl.2): 982-999. doi: 10.7752/jpes.2020.s2139.
35. Popovych IL, Gozhenko AI, Korda MM, Klishch IM, Popovych DV, Zukow W (editors). *Mineral Waters, Metabolism, Neuro-Endocrine-Immune Complex*. Odessa Feniks; 2022: 252.
36. Popovych IL, Kozyavkina NV, Barylyak LG, Vovchyna YV, Voronych-Semchenko NM, Zukow W, Tsybryla VV. Variants of changes in blood pressure during its three consecutive registrations. *Journal of Education, Health and Sport*. 2022; 12 (4): 365-375. doi.org/10.12775/JEHS.2022.12.04.032
37. Puig JG, Torres RJ, de Miguel E, S6nchez A, Bail6n R, Banegas JR. Uric acid excretion in healthy subjects: a nomogram to assess the mechanisms underlying purine metabolic disorders. *Metabolism Clinical & Experimental*. 2012; 61: 512-518. doi: 10.1016/j.metabol.2011.08.00
38. Ruzhylo SV, Tserkovnyuk AV, Popovych IL. Acetotropic Effects of Balneotherapeutic Complex of Truskavets spa [in Ukrainian]. Kyiv.Computerpress; 2003: 131.
39. Shannon CE. A mathematical theory of information. *Bell Syst Tech J*. 1948; 27: 379-423.
40. Shin DH. To treat or not to treat asymptomatic hyperuricemia in chronic kidney disease. *Kidney Res Clin Pract*. 2019; 38: 257-259. doi: 10.23876/j.krcp.19.074.
41. Shaffer F & Ginsberg JP. An Overview of Heart Rate Variability Metrics and Norms. *Front Public Health*. 2017; 5: 258. PMID: 29034226.
42. ĩukow X & Zavidnyuk YV. Glomerular filtration and diuresis are related to the state of lipids peroxidation in female rats exposed to water-salt loads accompanied by chronic stress. *Journal of Education, Health and Sport*. 2021; 11 (12): 481-491. http://dx.doi.org/10.12775/JEHS.2021.11.12.039

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